

CMIP6 Community Survey: Model Benchmarking and Evaluation Results

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2024-1-29

Citation: Lee, J. (2024). CMIP6 Community Survey: Model Benchmarking and Evaluation Results. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15478482>

Survey responders' Countries

This analysis of the CMIP6 community survey results, focused on responses related to model benchmarking and/or evaluation was carried out, and reported back to, the Model Benchmarking Task Team by Jiwoo Lee in January 2024. The survey was initially circulated on 14 January 2022, and responses were collected until 14 March 2022. 318 responses were submitted. The anonymised results relating to model benchmarking and evaluation can be found in this document. A summary of all the responses can be found in the CMIP6 Community Survey Results document: [CMIP6 Community Survey Results](#)

Extract: Relevant Comments

- DECK provides fundamental **benchmarking** capability to modelling groups both established and emerging. Historical forcings were later than anticipated. Historical forcings become outdated overtime. Suggest regularly updating the historical forcings dataset.
- An idealized CO2-only emissions scenario would help benchmark models with a coupled carbon cycle (e.g. 10 GtC/year, Krasting et al 2014).
- For PMIP we have been strict to make sure the simulations proposed in CMIP (only 5) are good references for the overall PMIP activity. We also insisted on the fact that 2 periods were present in PMIP since the beginning, which allow systematic **benchmarking** and evaluation of model evolution. This is way they are considered as entry cards, but to make it easy for groups it was mandatory to run on of them.
- Still a concern for PMIP event though it improves Need resources to help for this and gather information and script and/or include in existing tools (for systematic **benchmarking**) community is very diverse model-data in paleo is very diverse. flexibility is needed python notebooks seems promising
- How critical to your institution's mission, funding and/or internal or external priorities is participation in CMIP?: Very. A very important **benchmarking** activity and for impact from our modelling efforts.
- we are using CMIP simulations and experimental design in our model development process. This involves using CMIP simulations as a **benchmark** against which the impact of new developments or improvements are assessed. Simulations to quantify effective radiative forcings are increasingly being used in model development assessment and in our research analysis.

Extract: Relevant Comments (continued)

- CMIP is firstly a public service to IPCC to increase public awareness and confidence in climate science, but also a core coupled modeling community **benchmarking** effort. The DECK experiments help understand key aspects of a model and its fidelity.
- I think open and transparent model **benchmarking** and comparison is a very valuable function. I'd be tempted to leave the formal CMIP goals at that and have more specialised simulations, projections and comparison be left to outside efforts.
- The purposes of CMIP are to provide a **regular benchmark for climate modelling** (through inter-comparison), to provide a way to quantify structural and other types of uncertainties in relation to a few important research questions, and to form a bedrock for the development of climate services. Some of these purposes could be better achieved by including further model developers in the design of CMIP. The added value of a new MIP should be demonstrated to limit the number of "official" MIPs.
- The importance of **benchmarking regional climates** will increase but this may not require further simulations.

Extract: Relevant Comments (continued)

- The establishment of CMIP evaluation tools such as the ESMValTool in CMIP6 was a success
 - Facilitated the evaluation of the complex model ensemble with observations
 - Allowed for the first time to benchmark ensembles from different CMIP phases
 - ESMValTool used in several IPCC chapters which ensured quality control
 - A routine evaluation through these tools should be enabled in future phases, so that the tools run alongside the ESGF and can directly display evaluation results as the output is submitted.
 - In other words, the evaluation tools could be made part of the publication process of the data